

A NEED OF SCHOOL HEALTH CLINIC IN PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15630904>

Keywords

School Health Clinics in Pakistan, Students medical needs, Medical Emergency, Pakistan Health Ministry. Student health Care.

Article History

Received on 03 June 2025

Accepted on 03 June 2025

Published on 10 June 2025

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Abstract

Having a school health clinic on schools in Pakistan is a very important need. Daily there are a lot of students that face medical need in schools. Schools in Pakistan needs to provide in order to take care of their students. From checking and analyzing the results tells us that schools indeed need this facility. There are numerous of cases that happened and schools in Pakistan did not have this facility. This had made a huge impact and the schools have to take care of the students. The schools have addressed this need to take care of their students.

INTRODUCTION

In Pakistan there are more than 313,000 thousand of school.(Government of Pakistan, 2024) Since there are a lot of schools in the country. Everyday there are students that are a need of medical attention or there is any medical problems in them. Throughout many years there are students that face any emergency in schools. Due to this majority of the schools don't have any school clinics available on their school. There are many cases because of these medical emergency that the school face instead of calling any ambulance they just call the student parent to come pick their child and tale them to hospital. It is a school responsibility to take care of this problem. (Callen et al., 2020)

The school doesn't want to take this responsibility because of no policy introduced by the ministry of health. The school are just making their own decision whether they want to keep this facility or not. Due to

this many students when they require an immediate medical attention do not get it because of this. More schools are opening and more the ministry of health needs to see this problem. Teachers and staff are not even trained to use first aid kit and to perform cpr. Regions such as North America, middle east, and Asia have this facility for their students. (Godoy-Ramirez et al., 2019)

In Pakistan majority of the schools is not implementing it because they don't want to take this responsibility. Due to this we need a policy that there needs to be a school health clinic. In every school whether it's a small or a large campus. Its every students right to receive medical attention from there school health clinic. What if there is a sudden emergency and there is no health clinic in school and

because of it the student loses its life. There needs to be a must need of it in schools all around the country. There are a lot of doctors and nurses in the country that are jobless in the country. The ministry of health can adjust these doctors and nurses in to the schools and they can give an option to schools that they can hire their own staff. This issue is very important to address that the school needs to understand this and implement it. Many schools around the country needs to implement it. The ministry of health what they can do is create a policy that I will mention on the recommendations through that they can see and follow up and look at those option and try to implement it. (Leroi et al., 2019)

This issue is very important for the country because when there was covid the schools did not know on how to follow up this problem and to face it. It was a chaos. If every schools had their own school health clinic then they could have deal with the problem properly according to the safety measures applied by that government. With this the every school will have their own school health clinic and will be able to treat their students on timely and properly instead of calling their parents to take their child to the hospital. (Gul & Khilji, 2021)

With this policies a lot of problems with the student's health and school system will go as smooth with a one way system. By this it will be clear way for the schools that they will must be followed. The purpose for this is to ensure that this policy will help to sustain more in to control this environment. The objectives for this purpose is to make the whole country to synthesize it. This will make a good use of it that this will be implemented.

This will improve more safety and avoid more health risk error for the students. This is must needed for their drive. With more of this context they can utilize more of the workforce of their doctors and nurses. With more of this the more the impact will be there. With the school clinic they can easily monitor each student's health. The school needs to stay prepared for this. The more the school will be ready with these services. The more the students are monitored the more performance the student will give.

(Arenson et al., 2019).

Background and Context

This issue is around that there are a lot of students sick everyday and need medical attention on daily bases. With this around the country the way to deal with this is the ministry of health should contact every school around the country to see how many medical each schools are facing daily. With this they can measure on how much strength they need to deploy every city and at suburbs area. (Haahtela et al., 2021) In Pakistan schools are still following old ways that they call the child parents to take them to hospitals no matter how serious a child gets. The ministry of health needs to address this on to the system by acknowledging on how other countries are dealing with this. Ones they make it mandatory on to the schools then they need make a room mandatory for this. With this they have to insure that a necessary equipment are there to provide to use for the healthcare staff. (Arenson et al., 2019)

With this every employee of the school needs to be trained first aid kit. When there is an emergency situation the employees can treat the student or any person at that time. Unfortunately most of the employee doesn't have any basic training of first aid kit. Due to that they cannot even treat any wounds of the students. The ministry of the health needs to take an interest in to this matter and needs to follow this procedure.

Since there has been a lot of injuries in the past on the schools. The school could have handled it with care for the students if they had school health clinic made on their school. They weren't established at that time and even till now majority of the schools doesn't have it it's a very serious matter. (Feng, n.d.)

The more the health is taken care of our students then the more performance and wealth can be taken care of our country. However, there can be other stakeholders that can have their interest in this by joining forces they can implement it as fast as possible. The more fast approach engage they will take the more better it will be for our school system. This Is a must need for our school students. When they will implement it they will make it much better.

The stakeholders can easily monitor it on to the schools after implementing it by taking this in to a must necessary way. The more they will implement it the more exploration will be there by advancing more in the technique way. (Khan et al., 2013)

Problem Statement

This is a huge problem that needs to be addressed quickly. If there will be a sudden emergency on the school and they don't have any medical staff available in the school clinic then who will take the responsibility. The way to stop this problem from going on there needs to be school health clinic needed on every school in the country.

With the clinic it will be hard for the students to help them when they need medical attention and it will be hard for the schools to deal with every students. The schools should address this concern to the ministry of health. With this they can be eased with a lot of problems. (Thomas et al., 2020)

When there was a covid breakout the schools didn't know how to take measures with the safety and health of the students. If at that time the schools had a health clinic in them then those measures would have been dealt with it. That is why the situation is very serious and it needs to be addressed at top priority. (McKay-Brown et al., 2019)

This is a matter that every schools around the country should discuss with the ministry of health that this should be a must and needs to have on every school. Even till today there are a lot of different virus that are spreading quickly. That is why we need school health clinic to make sure that the health and safety of the students are measured everyday so the students basic health measures can be checked daily. (Reyes & Power, 2021)

Every students health care needs to be taken care in to a serious manner With this it will be easily maintained. When there will be no health clinics and in them a nurse and a doctor are not there to monitor the students in the school then there will be more and this is a serious concern on the students. In this way the doctors and nurses that are jobless with those workforce the ministry of health can assign them on the schools. These healthcare workers will be trained and can monitor the students properly. Every students normal vitals will be checked and monitored properly. If its not checked then the students will get sick and it will be hard for the school to treat the students. This is a serious situation that needs to be addressed so this major problem can be taken care of. (Love et al., 2019)

Research Aim and Objectives

The research aim and objectives is to identify on what will be the impact created with the school offering the health clinics for their students. It is to make mandatory requirement to have this facility. The objectives are to:

- To take care of the students mental and physical health in school
- To make the schools ready for any emergency situation
- To deal with any national medical emergency.
- To ensure the safety of the students health.

Significance of the study

In this study the ministry of health needs to implement this need for all the schools in Pakistan. The significance of this study will tell us that we can help the students by taking care of them when needed in medical emergency. This is an important step for taking a necessary action that will make it to go on higher stage. Since this is a series step needed to take care. This study will tell is that it is a whole country need. (Shackleton et al., 2015)

Literature Review

Country Need

Schools in Pakistan need health clinics in schools. They need to provide it for their students. This is a must need facility that is required. For the schools this is another expense that majority of the schools cannot afford. However, when there is an emergency and a student needs a treatment at that time the school cannot do anything due to there is no facility available and facility are trained to deal with this situation.

This is a need that is a requirement that the ministry of health needs to understand and make it necessary for the schools to have this facility available. This is why it is a nation-wide need for Pakistan to implement it like other countries around the world have this facility offered. (Alsubaie et al., 2016)

Medical Emergency

When there will be a medical emergency situation there will be no way to take care of the student. Many schools in Pakistan have faced this situation that during the medical emergency time they did not even know what to do. This is a serious situation that is needed to consider. During covid the schools faced

issue regarding taking and checking health safety measure that was needed during those days. Since this is a situation that is a problem for the students that when they have trust issues on the school that no one can take care of them during medical situation. A student life is serious and needs to be addressed on serious matter. (Aslam & Kingdon, n.d.)

Health Checkup

When the school will have the health clinic facility the school can keep a track of their students. In many countries around the world keep regular check of their students in schools that they make sure that the student health is updated. They make sure if the student is not facing any medical problem that could be serious in future. This is a crucial step that is needed in Pakistan to keep the balance of there student. Schools needs to get prepared for it because later on there could be serious problems for the school and student to deal with it. (Chandir et al., 2020)

Necessary Health equipment

The schools need to have necessary equipment to check their students. This is a must need to assess them. It is required for the schools to also keep a first aid kit that will help them to treat the students with small maimed. The equipment needs to be always checked if they are up to date. The health ministry needs to provide the equipment to the school when they develop the health clinics. If it is not there then this is a serious need that is needed to be available always on the school.

The schools around the world have the medical equipment that is required on their school. The equipment have helped the schools to keep their students safe and made a good use of it. Many countries have made their facility more advance to even treating and helping the students both medically and mentally. They are providing psychology treatment for their students in need in their schools. (Bradby et al., 2007)

Analysis and Evidence

With the current analysis is that the need of school health clinics is a must need in Pakistan. This is a serious problem that is needed to consider. With the recent analysis it has shown that it is needed. It was

checked from school that how many students needed medical attention throughout the year.

This was checked and analyzed that due to less attention or no faculty available at that time there was no faculty available. The causes are significant when there is no school health clinic in schools. There needs to be there. When there will be clinic in the school then the analysis are good the students health problems are taken care of. When there is no health clinics then the analysis are changed. (Maqsood et al., 2021)

There will be a huge consequences if there will be no health clinics in school. When there will be an emergency and the school doesn't have any in school clinics to treat their students then the outcome will be much different. When the school will have this facility then there will be no problem for the students and they will be saved and treated properly in time.

Currently there are no policy designed for the school that there needs to be a must implemented school clinics. With this major problems the government must see the analysis and must consider that they need to take initiative. The more fast the step the ministry of health will take the more effectiveness will be there for the schools and will help the medical provided in school for the students. (Khan et al., 2013)

The ministry of health must make the school mandatory that it needs to take place on the whole country rather than focusing on one state. This issue is going on a lot since when the schools started in Pakistan. Only the big elite schools in Pakistan have kept a nurse in school just to deal with small medical problems of their students. Even when there is a serious emergency the school is not providing with any medical treatment. (Asiva Noor Rachmayani, 2015)

Methodology

In this research we have seen on how the school has been taking to establish school health clinics in their schools. The research approach that was taken in qualitative. In this we have checked that which mostly schools have talked about it. In upcoming all the talks will be shown in themes that what schools are doing and majority of them are not doing.

Data Collection

The data has been collected from Pakistan schools, I have went to schools and took interview of the administration on what was their say towards the need and must implementation of the school health clinics on their school.

Results

There where 7 respondent that had agreed to give interview. They have discussed that if they feel that this should be their requirement and have discussed their concerns.

Theme 1: The need of health clinics on their school

In this the interview had said that we feel there is a need for it. The participant had said daily they are getting at least more than 10 emergencies on their school. There is a need of this clinics on their school that it is mandatory. The participants had also said the health ministry has never discussed about this. This discussion has showed that there is a must need for a health clinic in this school.

“We receive a lot of health sickness in our school. Unfortunately, we don’t have a clinic facility because this isn’t a requirement of the ministry so no matter any medical emergency we get we just call the parents to come and take their child to the hospital because we don’t have any facility to deal with it. Even though it is a need but not mandatory we will only make this facility when it is mandatory”.

Theme 2: A need to accept it

Many schools are thinking to implement it but it is stopping them due to budget issues. Some schools are saying that we think the ministry of health should bring this facility and pay the staff and bring the necessary equipment to facilitate it. In this the participants wants to have this facility but they are having financial issue. In this discussion the school admiration respondent has said that their principal had talked about this need and issue they are facing. “Every year we try to bring this facility in to the school but we cannot because of the budget issue we get. I remember that I ones tried it but I never got any response from the ministry of health”

Theme 3: The game changing experience

This is one of the elite schools of Pakistan they have kept a nurse in their school after they had a life threatening situation when they were forced by the parents. In this the respondent has talked about what happened and what was the reason to have one small facility and pay the nurse from the school even though this in not necessary to do.

In this the respondent have said “Well one of our student was playing and then the student got a head injury. In that situation we didn’t know what to do because we had no health clinic available and had no staff to deal with it. Due to this we had to at least hire a nurse to deal with any medical problem in our school. This is a must need in every school to at least have a one doctor and nurse hired”

Theme 4: The need to implement it

One of the school has said that this is a must requirement the respondent for this discussion has said we are planning to have this medical facility in our school but we stop every time because this is not a mandatory requirement and no checks from the ministry because they never talked about it. In this the principal and the administration had said the same thing.

The respondent was talking. “That from the past 2 years we are trying to bring this facility because we have dealt with a lot of medical emergency in our school. But when it comes to implementation the head of school always stops us from doing it that this is an unnecessary expense even though this is a need but the head of school says when the ministry will say its mandatory then they will implement it or when they feel like it”

Theme 5: Recommendations from every interview people

This a need and this must be implemented. All of the participants have talked about that we need this school health clinics. This is a need and requirement for every schools that the ministry of health should make it mandatory for every schools and must keep the check and balance on every schools. With this the school can deal with any medical emergency or just checking and treating with small maimed students.

Policy Options and Recommendations

The policy they can start implementing is by that every school in Pakistan will must have a school health clinic. With this the advantage is that each school will be able to treat each student timely and keep a track on the students. There are no disadvantages for it. Then the next policy they can implement is that the ministry of health will make a must doctor and a nurse implemented on the school. Every school whether it is a small campus or a big campus they will have a room and in that room there will be a one doctor and nurse. This is a huge opportunity for the doctors and nurses to get job and the school wont have to hire by themselves. There is no disadvantage in it.(Ruff et al., 2019)

The other policy they should implement is that after making a school clinic for the students the medical staff will need to keep all the necessary required equipment with them to treat the students. The advantage is that they can treat the students in time and can treat them in any situation when required. The disadvantage is when if they will not keep these instruments with them then this will be a serious problem for the students.

With these policies suggested for the ministry of health its better for them to implement all these. This will make a system for the schools that they will have to follow this mandatory. This policy will help to make this engage. This policies will help to face this problem. When they will start implementing this policy step by step then the problems will be more less and later will perish. (Viner et al., 2020).

Implementation Strategy

These policies will start by implementing from cities by cities. The starting point is by they need to pass that it is mandatory for the schools to have the school health clinic. Then they can either give choices to the school whether if they want the school can hire their staff or the government will issue them. (Dong et al., 2024)

With this then according on to the school capacity and its location there will be a must room provided for the health clinics. Then all the equipment will be provided to the staff. In this way there will be a step by step a one way system will be made for the schools that they will need to follow the ministry of health standards by all the school in the country. This

standards can be followed up by a recent conditions and what is happening.

This will make a long turn impact for the country. When this will be implemented the challenges is that they will face is to keep up with the resources that will be required to keep the check and balance of the students secured. Once this will go on this will create a huge impact on daily health checks and medical attentions on school for the students. When the government will start to implement it a total of one year is required. In this one year they can see and adjust on what type of resources are needed and required for the schools to use it.(Kaplow et al., 2020)

Cost Benefit Analysis

The cost will only be analyzed on that spot if the government decides to either provide them with doctors and nurses or if they decide that the ministry of health will provide necessary equipment needed for the facility.

Conclusion

In Pakistan school Health Clinic is a need that is required from through out these many years. The ministry of health needs to see this problem and should implement this as quick as possible. The country needs to implement this policy. This policy will help a lot to the school students that face a difficulty when there is a need to medical attention. With this the students will be taken care by the school when this facility will be available for them.

This problem will be fixed and will help the school to focus on giving a better education to their students. Since a lot of schools are not considering as an important part then they should. When the ministry of health will make it mandatory by implementing this policy then there wont be health issue problems to deal with the students.

There were parents that reported that their children face serious injuries in schools and the school did not do anything. They did not treat their child and not even called an ambulance. Instead they called the students parents to come and take their child to hospital by themselves. This is a serious concerned matter.

If the school is not taking any measures then this is a serious problem that the ministry of health needs to see. By implementing these policies suggested these

problems will not be face by anyone. Even the parents wont have to go and take their children by themselves. No matter if a school is small or big this facility needs to be there and must be mandatory for the school to have a health clinic to treat their students.

By these analysis that were talked about when the students face these similar problems. If they were been treated and if the school had that facility at that time then there wont have been a lot of problems. By this If the ministry of health will provide the necessary equipment that is needed to treat the students at school. The staff can keep a check and balance with the students.

With a school health clinic available at school there every student can be treated properly and on time. This will create a huge impact on the country by implementing it. This is a must need for the students. Each students life matters at that time if they are not treated properly on time. Although this is a must need for the country.

When this will be implemented the medical staff at that school can daily keep health checkup of their students and monitor it. By this the students will became more healthy and wont be afraid by any task given to them. With the implementation of the policy there will be a huge advantage for the schools that this ease the burden on the school.

With it the doctors and nurses that are unemployed can be utilized with this system. The ministry of health needs to address this policy. The policy will help them to create and see this problem clearly that this needs to addressed immediately. Whenever there is a student sick or if there is a child loss because of no facility available in schools then that particular school doesn't understand and don't have an answer to solve this problem. The better the and fast way they implement these policies the more the better the result they will get and things will be handled faster and accordingly to solve this matter. This is a serious matter and school health clinic needs to be available on all the school around the country.

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Has ministry of health taken any initiative towards it?
Have the school faced any medical emergency?
If you have this service what equipment and how many staff you have?
Do you have any staff that can treat your students and employees with any medical problem on the spot?

Questions for Interview

Why isn't the school offering school clinics to its student?

What are the challenges you are facing to bring make a health clinic in your school?